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REVIEW OF THE DATA LANDSCAPE

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1. Introduction: Enhancing Data Findability and Accessibility

Computational Literary Studies (CLS) communities require tools and services that are customized with a specific focus on literary data. The data should be not only domain-specific, but also of high quality, i.e. user-centric, findable, accessible, and reusable. To reduce effort and time, researchers wish to locate and explore already existing resources, while compiling corpora by drawing on different resources, and oftentimes using different textual collections.

“There is surprisingly little discussion of corpora in DH” (Piotrowski 2022: 6). According to CLS INFRA’s D4.1,¹ the most glaring gap between the supply and the demand in CLS training concerns corpus design and access frameworks. This is precisely the gap this landscape review will try to fill. We aim at enhancing the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of literary data, which is usually stored in collections, in corpora. We advocate for the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016) by introducing a tentative order into the plethora of literary text collections already available online in order for the members of the community to know what to expect from a collection, i.e. what can most probably be found in a corpus. Unsurprisingly, metadata, their quality, and their structure are a recurrent motive of the present document.

This landscape review, for which Work Package 5 is responsible, focuses on intellectual access, i.e. providing guidance for finding and sharing literary data, while Work Package 6 approaches the task from a more technological side, collecting and analyzing literary corpora, available formats, tools, and metadata in order to create an exploratory catalogue / inventory of literary corpora and to provide a transformation matrix/toolbox for solving common issues. Yet we coordinate our efforts – beginning with the compilation of the table of literary collections – therefore one can regard these as two sides of the same coin.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/6421513>.

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The review's point of departure is the abundance of existing data and their diversity or heterogeneity as regards corpus design and underlying concepts, for example the definitions of text (is it a source, an edition, a data set? see chapter 3), the purpose of a corpus (e.g. general, reference, or monitoring corpora, special purpose corpora; see chapter 4), central considerations or criteria regarding the construction of a corpus (sampling, balancing, representativeness, annotation model(s), data format(s); see likewise chapter 4). How can I go about obtaining data without transgressing ethical or legal boundaries (see chapter 5)? We ask: How can we assist literary scholars in searching for and finding existing data that are relevant to their own research questions? And additionally, what kind of research question is relevant concerning the present-day state of the data landscape and literariness and textuality?

The intended addressees of the review are literary scholars pursuing CLS or simply interested in this kind of research, but we think that also die-hard, seasoned, and accomplished CLS researchers can take a step back and reflect on the nature of their object (text) and the ensuing position of the discipline in relation to literary and textual studies in general.

Our first task consists of identifying vantage points from which to look at the data landscape. For this purpose, we draw on D3.1² (a bibliometrical study of CLS research papers), but we have also initiated a cooperation with the data curation specialists acting in the flagship program in CLS of the German Research Foundation; they survey researchers to identify the most relevant problems of the field.³ In this way, we combine bibliometrical objectivity with the mapping of the consciousness of researchers, or the third- and first-person perspectives. By doing so, we can single out the central notions of CLS which are relevant to the focus of our study.

At all times we remember that our goal is limited to providing orientation and is not an exhaustive map of the resources available (cf. WP6). Any CLS researcher understands that the representation of a field also inevitably entails the reduction of its

² <https://zenodo.org/record/6389333>.

³ <https://dfg-spp-cls.github.io/about.html>.

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complexity. We are aware that what we present here is just one of many possible approaches and a result of different attitudes attributable to our diverse backgrounds. And even though our use cases and general observations sometimes prompt us to formulate various recommendations regarding metadata (materializing in D6.1.), we nevertheless always try to describe what is, and never to prescribe what should be.

Now, for the blueprint of the present review. After a short introduction to our research cases (chapter 2), we map in chapter 3 the research context or, more precisely, the nature of literary data in the digital paradigm. We acknowledge that contemporary CLS is, on the one hand, not the first branch of literary studies to use statistical and algorithmic methods, and that, on the other hand, CLS encompasses much more than applying calculations and data processing to collections of literary texts, namely editing, visualizing, annotating, etc. What is specific about CLS is the centrality of large machine-readable corpora that entail remixing and re-contextualization of existing resources, most conspicuously new numerical methods developed in Natural Language Processing (NLP) and corpus / computational linguistics. By the same token, the paradigm has a huge impact on the basic notions of literary studies, such as literariness and textuality alongside the text's relation to the collection, which becomes much more intimate and intricate in comparison with traditional libraries. We accordingly analyze the meaning of all components of the nominal group "the collection of literary texts".

In a next step, taken in chapter four, we propose a typology (not ontology) of existing collections in consideration of their purpose, which determines their structure. We describe general-purpose collections (such as Wikisource, HathiTrust, Gutenberg: these are sources that need to be mined or scraped); subcorpora of reference corpora (in linguistics, reference corpora are supposed to render a general image of a language, the language of literature is treated as a register of language); digital critical editions; monitor corpora (ELTeC,⁴ DraCor⁵ – in linguistics, a monitor corpus is supposed to make possible the tracing of changes in a language; we use the term to refer to collections curated with

⁴ The abbreviation stands for European Literary Text Collection: <https://www.distant-reading.net/eltec/>.

⁵ Drama Corpora Project: dracor.org.

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particular care, leaning towards “programmable corpora” in the sense of Fischer et al. 2019); corpora compiled on the basis of a research question; and finally opportunistic corpora that rely on what is readily available. Corpus opportunism corresponds to the goal of the landscape review, pointing to already existing resources, without however compromising the quality of research.

In the same fourth chapter, we also account for key considerations regarding the selection and sampling of texts (criteria are relative to different types of corpora). We account for corpus architecture alongside basic qualities such as completeness, representativeness, proportion (balance), and frequent biases. We loyally warn our readers of paradoxes hidden in these apparently clear and obvious features, for example the conflict between proportion and representativeness. We also cover some issues concerning the retrieval of the data, even though we are aware of the fact that this part of our report will become outdated sooner than our considerations on intellectual access as well as intellectual property, to which chapter five is devoted (legal and ethical issues).

2. Reference Case Studies Highlighting Research Context and Corpus Design

(Haiku, Slovak Novel)

Since there is an endless number of ways in which the complexity of the data landscape can be reduced, we have formulated two use cases to guide us through the thicket and point our attention to eminent features of the research context and of corpus design. Besides, concreteness helps us shape our narration and – as we hope – grab the readers’ attention. To cover as much ground as possible, we tried to come up with two polar-opposite instances of data trouble: the haiku and the Slovak novel. The former is exotic and yet abundant in multilingual corpora, endowed with the prestige of Anglophone and global High Modernism; the latter is an overlooked outsider of Central European literary culture.

The case of looking for the haiku across multilingual collections illustrates in chapter 3 the qualities the texts gain in the digital paradigm as the most general context for CLS. It moreover shows the importance of metadata and the dependence of the

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findability of literary forms on data formats. In a widely read and discussed study,⁶ Hoyt Long and Richard Jean So (2016) treat the haiku as a “literary pattern” to be recognized by learning machines. Their work, on the one hand, exemplifies high-quality research in CLS as an instance of the digital paradigm; the paradigm affects the notion of literariness and literary essences, the status of text, a tension between modelling and exploring. On the other hand, their research is based on tacit assumptions concerning the construction and the compilation of corpora. We try to make these presuppositions explicit and describe our attempts to construct our own corpus, while expanding the scope of the search to collections in different languages.

The second case study, i.e. an attempt to compile an ELTeC-affine corpus of the Slovak novel, demonstrates above all the cultural implications regarding eligibility, representativeness, and balance as sought-for qualities of corpora. The work on the corpus puts into sharp relief the fragmentary character of the present-day data landscape in terms of both technical and intellectual accessibility (including inadequate metadata) of resources not produced by global players in the field of culture. We find it symptomatic that Slovak literature fell off the radar of the COST Action leading to ELTeC and only since autumn 2021 has a research group led by Marek Debnár of the University of Nitra been working on a comprehensively annotated full-text digital collection of Slovak prose up to 1951 in TEI format. The questions of epistemic injustice (cf. Byskov 2021) come to mind.

The corpus of the Slovak novel illustrates both our typology (not ontology!) of literary corpora and the central considerations concerning corpus design, such as eligibility. Political dependency and religious strife alongside the rural character of the country – circumstances impacting the system of literary genres and the imagery of literary works tending towards messianism rather than realism – render the decision as to whether a work is a novel extremely difficult. The linguistic situation is equally intricate, since standard Slovak was agreed on as late as 1843, and the orthography even later in

⁶ 70 citations according to the Google Scholar on May 30, 2022, <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=1262480556721891630>.

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the nineteenth century, while literary works regarded as pertaining to Slovak culture were also written in Latin and other languages of the region. As a product of a so-called small or minor culture, the Slovak novel highlights the discrepancy between the qualities of completeness, representativeness, and balance. The paucity of texts, conditional on continual repression, disturbs the relations between the sample and the population.

3. Research Context: Impact of the Digital Paradigm on Literary Text Collections

We describe in this chapter the impact of the digital paradigm on the understanding of the literary text and its relation to textual collections; the relation between the text and the corpus becomes more complex and intimate than in a traditional notion of an aggregate of texts. The digital paradigm encompasses – alongside its most noticeable element, i.e. quantitative (mostly statistical and algorithmic) methods employed previously in corpus linguistics and Natural Language Processing / Natural Language Understanding – visualization, data and metadata curation, digital editions, and annotation frameworks and guidelines. Research on literature conducted in the digital paradigm is known under different names: “distant reading” (Moretti 2005), “macroanalysis” (Jockers 2013), “cultural analytics” (Manovich 2016), “data-rich literary studies” (Bode 2018), and “Computational Literary Studies” (Da 2019; cf. Bode 2020). The Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) defines Computational Literary Studies (CLS) as “an emerging interdisciplinary research field at the intersection of literary studies and computer science aiming to apply computational methods to digitized literary texts to learn more on literary history, narratology or literary writing style.”⁷

From among the disciplines making up the interdisciplinary digital paradigm, especially corpus linguistics and NLP have bequeathed to CLS a series of methodological assumptions concerning both the techniques and the objects of textual analysis. These assumptions to a large extent determine what can be found in the abundant data landscape and what remains excluded from the field.

⁷ <https://dfg-spp-cls.github.io/about.html>

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In this chapter, we rely on the bibliometrical findings contained in D3.1 as well as the surveys of researchers conducted by the participants of the central project of the DFG's flagship program Computational Literary Studies. We endeavour to put the detailed results in a broader methodological perspective by relating them to the question of how all the widespread methods, tools, and data formats pertaining to CLS influence the meaning and applicability of the basic notions of literary studies: literature, text, and collection.

We relate all our deliberations in this chapter to the use case of the haiku. In their acclaimed albeit controversial study, Hoyt Long and Richard Jean So lean on Machine Learning and Natural Language Processing to introduce "literary pattern recognition" (2016). Their approach appears, on the one hand, to organically grow out of the methodological assumptions of CLS and thus exemplify our contentions regarding the digital paradigm. On the other hand, we point out what the hidden presuppositions and tacit practices concerning the construction of the corpus may be upon which a study like theirs can be carried out. We then describe our attempts to construct a corpus of the haiku in today's data landscape.

Before we embark on a detailed reconstruction of the notions of the literary, the textual, and the collecting, we would like to make clear one general point concerning CLS's research context. The digital paradigm cannot be reduced to statistical and computational methods, which have been present in literary studies for more than a century. Wincenty Lutosławski introduced the notion and rudimentary practice of stylometry as early as the 1890s (Lutosławski 1897), while Andrei Bely's statistical surveys of the rhythm of Pushkin's verse impress the readers of today with their refinement, including highly diagnostic and expressive visualizations (Bely 1929). Predominantly the Formalist-Structuralist branch of literary studies rounded up some great number crunchers: Boris Iarkho, Kazimierz Wóycicki, Franciszek Siedlecki, Maria Renata Mayenowa, Jerzy Woronczak, A. Q. Morton, and others. Many non-Structuralists understood the need to expand the textual basis of their research, e.g. Eva Becker (1964), Albert Ward (1974), Cornelia Mönch (1993), and the record holder Benjamin Herbst

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(2018), who based his dissertation on a traditional reading of six hundred dramas. What characterizes CLS is not counting in itself but the combination of editorial, annotational, visualizing, and *specific* mathematical methods, which enrich literary scholarship thanks to the renewal of cooperation with linguistics. While literary studies were looking away, the science of language and cognitive science adapted and developed highly advanced mathematical approaches that have very little in common with either the rudimentary statistics of the precursors in literary studies or the mathematics of ‘formal grammars’ of the generativists (see Gadkij and Mel’čuk 1973). It suffices to say that such a relatively user friendly and popular research tool of stylometry as Stylo (Eder, Rybicki and Kestemont 2016) embeds textual data in a one-hundred dimensional vector space to determine their proximity or affinity. (For a more detailed, albeit accessible to humanists, discussion of contemporary stylometry, see Büttner et al. 2017; Lauer and Jannidis 2014).

As a result of literary studies’ departure from linguistics after the demise of Structuralism, the questions of poetics and literary morphology gave way to cultural and political considerations, included under umbrella terms such as “discourse” or “narrative”. This is not to say that no groundbreaking studies of verse or, even more, of narrative were undertaken. However, the advent of CLS marks a turn towards linguistics as it is today and, consequently, a revival of poetics and literary morphology. It is nonetheless a different linguistics than in the first half of the twentieth century, when structural phonology gave cues to anthropology, literary studies, and practically any other branch of the humanities. CLS appropriates and adapts the methods developed in the two dominating strands of contemporary linguistics – corpus linguistics and NLP. Both branches of the knowledge of language use computers to process immense volumes of textual data, using algorithmic and statistical methods. Their upsurge was enabled by the advancement of the computational powers of machines and the advent of approaches competing with deductive approaches, such as most notably generative-transformational grammar. The development of NLP took the path from deductive algorithms to statistical models, e.g. attaching a statistical weight to each occurrence of a linguistic phenomenon in a given linguistic context. “You shall know a word by the company it keeps” (Firth 1957:

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11) seems to be a ubiquitous principle. In literary studies, this shift maps onto the difference between Algirdas Julien Greimas's general model of narrative (the semiotics of narrative action) and a classifier recognizing tragedies among an aggregate of different kinds of texts by relying on regularities of style and a chart of the average death toll per act.

3.1. "Literary" (Return of Essentialism, Poetics, and Classifications)

All three component parts of the notion "literary text collection" have brought with them their specific problems and undergone significant shifts since they were pulled into the field of the digital paradigm. With regard to what is "literary", CLS tends to opt for an essentialist stance in the ongoing discussions regarding the existence of and the need for the signpost of literariness and fictionality as well as stable quintessences of literary genres (cf. Bode 1997; Schaeffer 2007; Heilmann 2011; Jeziorska-Haładyj 2013). Literary theory and broader literary and cultural studies lean towards an anti-essentialist stance, according to which the mere existence of a signpost of literariness, poeticity, fictionality, etc. is controversial. Outside CLS, the consensus exists that there are no formal criteria for distinguishing literary from non-literary texts – in contradistinction to (likewise not so obvious) differences between verse language and prose. Rather, different compositional forms cross boundaries between pragmatical, everyday communication and literary utterances, for if literature has a mimetic character than it is in relation to everyday linguistic forms, shaped by and shaping different societal contexts. The quality of literariness is not given to a feature or a form once and for all. The silent drift of literary studies towards cultural studies pertains to Post-structuralism, hermeneutics, cultural studies, queer studies, gender studies, etc. This is usually the tacitly adopted default position as hardly anyone voices concerns over the limits of the literary.

The seminal work of the OPOIAZ (the Leningrad wing of Russian Formalism), regarded generally as one of the originators if not the originator of modern literary theory, is a case in point. In the same article in which Roman Jakobson famously states that the object of literary studies is not literature as an aggregation of texts and facts about their

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authors but literariness, i.e. the distinctive qualities of texts regarded as literary, he also introduces the principle of literary evolution as a metabolism between literature and its non-literary linguistic context – a metabolism consisting in a continual exchange of forms (Jakobson 1921). Therefore, there are no linguistic signposts of literariness (for example, fictionality stems from the pragmatic attitude of the subject and the reader towards the said). Some features become literary only to later lose this status.

And yet, Andrew Piper believes he has trained a classifier to distinguish fiction from non-fiction (Piper 2016) or detect narrativity (Piper, Bagga and Monteiro 2021). But does the model represent the essence of narrativity or did the researchers aggregate a mixture of heterogeneous features, combining grammatical terminology with Gérard Genette’s catachreses (“voice”, “mood” meaning something completely different than in linguistics; Piper et al. 2021: 326), which in a certain period were borrowed from non-fiction and applied to fictional discourse only to dissipate again, disappearing from inventive literature, which was fed up with marquises leaving the house at five, while the publishing market explores the inertia of the public’s taste?

Whatever your position, the formation of CLS brings about an approach according to which “literature” corresponds to a “system” of genres, whereby some genres are more literary than others, so that a novel appears to be more literary than an essay (this is an assumption behind ELTeC; on the machine-based recognition of literariness, see van Cranenburgh et al. 2019). In Long and So’s study – a part of our use case – the highly conventional genre haiku serves as an emblem of highbrow literariness, supposedly typical of literary Modernism.

Poetics, understood as the morphological study of literature, celebrates its comeback in CLS as research concentrates on (combinations of) formal features posited as features of a literary essence, like genre and technique (stream of consciousness in Long and So 2016a; haiku, narrativity, fictionality, novella, drama, etc.). CLS cannot forgo making use of clear taxonomies: corpora devoid of taxonomies likewise lack structure and significance. Of course, the comeback also means a makeover, especially considering

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almost exclusively linguistic features of the genre at the expense of the dimensions of the world represented (see Gittel and Köppe 2022).

The revival of literary essentialism in the context of Big Data depends on:

- A. The need of a relatively new discipline to establish itself alongside the well-defined limits of its field and its methods.
- B. The need for organizing and consolidating textual collections (or corpora) so that they become more findable, accessible, and reusable. These requirements compel the labelling of texts with specific metadata (cf. chapter 4 below).
- C. Predictive models, hailing from machine learning, likewise push the discipline in the direction of essentialism. Essentialism is hereditary. A number of methods employed in CLS come from AI and machine learning – for example classifiers, i.e. algorithms that utilize some training data (in most cases data annotated by humans) to assess how new material they come across relates to a class – is this piece of writing a narrative or not? The classifier “thinks” in binary categories as it must decide whether a text belongs to a group or not (e.g. Piper 2016; Piper et al. 2021; Underwood 2016).

However, the essentialism of CLS does not amount to a naive dogmatism as it is counterweighted by supplementing predictive models with descriptive and “understanding” ones (Piper 2016 9ff.; Underwood 2016) as well as thinking in degrees (intensity) and probabilities rather than absolutes (Piper et al. 2021). With regard to relativizing the mechanistic binary, Jonas Kuhn (2019) put forward the abduction of “rapid prototyping” or “the rapid probing” method from software engineering and applying it to CLS so that the method can mediate between the computational and the hermeneutical practice, with their different workflows and different temporalities. The proposition makes up a central part of the more general proposition of “reflexive algorithmic text analysis” advanced by the members of the Center for Reflected Text Analytics affiliated with the University of Stuttgart (CRETA 2020).

Other researchers shift their interest from the essence of a genre to laying bare tacit assumptions that drove historical instances of the delimitation of genres or the anthologization of their eminent specimen; Fotis Jannidis (2017) reconstructs the criteria

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behind the compilation of “Novellenschatz” undertaken by Paul Heyse and Hermann Kurz. Christian Schöch (2017) explores with the tools of topic modelling the contents related to the established genres of the French classical drama.⁸

As a result of liberalizing their essentialism, researchers fall into old Structuralist patterns, such as Roman Jakobson’s proclamation that the guiding thread of his research was the relation between invariants and variants (Jakobson 1985). In this vein, Long and So write: “[Computation] allows us to reconstruct shared structural patterns while identifying degrees of difference in sameness constitutive of the structure itself. Ultimately, computation generates theoretical space where apprehensions of texts as constitutive of structures or as radically singular can coexist, illuminating world literature as both structure and divergence, diffusion and variance” (Long and So 2016a: 347). Generally, “[s]tructure and variance [...] go hand in hand” (Long and So 2016a: 366).

Interestingly, essentialism in CLS corresponds to anti-dogmatism, which, for its part, fits together with the transparency of research decisions expressed in the documentation: “Uncertainty is part of the research process and acknowledging and quantifying this uncertainty is one of the core features that distinguishes computational research from more traditional forms of analysis” (Piper 2020: 33).

3.2. “Text” (between Bag of Words and Ordered Hierarchy of Content)

Maciej Eder (Eder et al. 2016) points out the ways in which the computational methods revolutionized the notion of the text: “Traditionally understood as a vehicle of (hypothesized) authorial intention, the text became a sequence of characters bearing some information. A careful philological attitude towards author’s words was replaced by: (1) distant reading, which in fact means analysis involving no reading at all, (2) focusing on the most frequent words rather than on elaborated rare vocabulary, (3) distorting the original word order by applying the “bag-of-words” model of analysis, (4) high tolerance to textual errors, e.g. imperfect OCR. Such a deep redefinition, however, allows for assessing the history of literature on an unprecedented scale.”

⁸ For a substantial criticism of topic modelling, see Shadrova (2021).

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Both corpus linguistics and NLP – the two model disciplines of CLS – show a specific understanding of their object which some literary scholars may find off-putting. The text, considered not for itself, but as a part of a big collection, has a value and significance not for its own sake, but only in relation to a bigger whole of which it is a part; this part itself is decomposable into linguistic elements whose proper context is the whole collection rather than a single text. Precisely such elements are of importance and of interest because they can be submitted to statistical and other computational methods. Computational methods often track the behaviour of a singular item (word, phrase) across the whole collection of texts.

What CLS does to the text strikes one as even more paradoxical than its essentialist-skeptical take on literariness. Text or the text⁹ appears, on the one hand, as an “ordered hierarchy of content objects” (OHCO); the Text Encoding Initiative likewise defines text as a fixed and hierarchically ordered artifact, where attributes can be inherited.¹⁰ The hierarchy distinguishes strictly between the text and metatext (annotations – see chapter 4). On the other hand, most computational methods ignore syntax. Like the Futurists and Dadaists more than a hundred years ago, researchers liberate words from their established positions and put them into “bags of words”. They are counted for their quantity, not the position in the utterance. However, the CLS researcher’s task is more difficult than Tzara’s pulling words out of hat. As Gavin points out, “against the commonly held notion” counting words does not reduce complexity. A typical procedure transforms a text “into a simple list of words and their frequencies, then to a vector of elements in a matrix” (Gavin 2020: 4), arriving at a highly complex structure, where “words and documents are mutually constituted by the linear transformation of lexical space into bibliographical space. Because every document is a system of words made of documents; every word, a system of documents made of words. Rather than say

⁹ Caton (2013) points out that in DH the term *text* occurs with both mass and count noun senses. Of the three characteristics of “a scholarly edition (considered the normative instance of a countable text)”, the “written representation of language” and “intent to communicate” pertain to *text* in the mass. The third characteristic – that the communication be complete within its bounds – can lead to endowing *text* (mass) with the status of *a text*, however only in some contexts and contingent on our choosing: “countable” *text* is therefore not a type but a role. “[S]ome text* is always potentially *a text*” (p. 218).

¹⁰ <https://tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/ST.html#STEC>.

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we're representing a document as a series of word frequencies, it's more accurate to say that each text is represented as a structured set of historically relevant relations to historically relevant contexts" (Gavin 2020: 13). Emancipated from the shackles of syntax, the word finds itself in a new structure that represents relationships among all elements in the text or a textual collection. Furthermore, even if CLS, following NLP, does reduce complexity of meaning, so does traditional literary interpretation, proof of which is delivered by the co-existence of many brilliant, compelling, and mutually exclusive readings of classic works of literature. Each of these interpretations reduces the complexity of a literary utterance in its own way.

However, both extremes of the digital notion of text, hierarchy and bagginess, still belong to one specific vision of text that is perceived as an artifact, not an event; a fixed sequence of linguistic signs rather than a unique significant occurrence possible only in a certain context. Remarkably, text linguistics has since the 1960s and 1970s opted for the latter view of the text: "the individual communicative event within the ongoing interaction of discourse" (de Beaugrande 2011: 292).

The counting methods give priority to the graphemic notion of text (writing historically derives from first attempts to fix numbers of things, so called tally marks, Lunde and Miura 2015). For this reason, our landscape review limits itself to collections of graphemic texts, leaving aside recordings of textual performances, corpora of spoken discourse, and the like. We are aware of our choice's not only technical, but also cultural motivation (our rootedness in European culture, which has undergone the Gutenbergian revolution and favours sight and operations on discrete entities). Moreover, we acknowledge the existence of textual resources that, on the one hand, belong to the heart of European literature and, on the other hand, transcend the "plain" sequential text, as for example the poetry of the Avant-garde (not only "Concrete Poetry").

In our use case, Long and So are not looking for typical formal features of poems that would qualify as a haiku, but instead they dismantle poems into bags of words and lemmatize them (group together inflected or variant forms of the same word), having filtered out stop words (articles, prepositions, pronouns, conjunctions, and the like).

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Therefore, what the machine is actually learning is not so much to recognize forms (“patterns” = “forms”) but rather to place on the shelf “haiku” a bag containing full words that appear in the haiku more often than other words (“pattern” = “tendency”).

3.3. Modelling vs. Exploratory Approaches to Textual Data

Researchers hailing from qualitative literary studies should be mindful of an approach to data – and, consequently, to corpus design – that has lately become a distinguishing characteristic of a large portion of CLS research. The exploratory approach to data has been gaining ground in CLS at the expense of the more traditional modelling methods. The most animated discussion in recent years about the fundamentals of CLS – provoked by Nan Da’s noted (or, for some, notorious) article (Da 2019) – has revolved around the problem of exploration *vis-à-vis* modelling. The debate has left the impression that the entanglement of the two approaches, inherent in present-day CLS, leads to many misunderstandings and misperceptions that concern, among others things, the design of scholarly corpora.¹¹ Most notably, confusion reigns in the conceptualizations of the relation between the sample and the pool, which lies at the centre of any theory of corpus.

Ted Underwood points out in his response to Da that she and her like-minded colleagues fail to differentiate between predictive modelling, exploratory data analysis, and explanation: “exploratory analysis and predictive modeling aim at goals different from explanation and need to be evaluated differently” (Underwood 2020: 905). Exploration does not amount to testing pre-existing hypotheses concerning the population or the relation between data and population but looks for interesting patterns in data themselves.

By embracing the exploratory approach, CLS is re-enacting the discussions provoked by Post-structuralism in qualitative literary studies concerning the notions of Truth and the Signified as opposed to the Signifier. The proponents of data exploration intend to do away with the distinction between true and false interpretations or, as one of them put it, “a zerosum mentality in how literary scholars often evaluate arguments: either

¹¹ Critical Inquiry set up a blog featuring the discussion around the article:
<https://critinq.wordpress.com/2019/03/31/computational-literary-studies-a-critical-inquiry-online-forum/>.

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you buy a reading or you don't, and if you don't, that interpretation needs to be displaced or ignored" (So 2017: 669). According to Underwood (2019: 178), researchers no longer must decide which of any conflicting samples (more) correctly represents the population, i.e. what the case was. He instead proposes exploring the differences between the results they yield. Such an attitude parallels the problematization of the truthfulness–fictionality distinction in the literary studies of the second half of the twentieth century and the proliferation of literary theories perceived as creative activity in its own right: "Instead of foregrounding incompatible differences between models, Roman Frigg has emphasized the diversity of representational approaches within models" (Piper 2017: 653; cf. Frigg and Nguyen 2017). Likewise, as in Post-structuralism, exploratory "models shift the focus toward the signifiers of research and away from the signifieds" (Piper 2017: 652). Cutting-edge research in CLS – e.g. Ted Underwood, Andrew Piper, and Richard Jean So – dissociate samples from populations, as the ideal of representativeness supposedly stifles "computational innovation and weigh[s] quantitative literary studies down with the requirement, if not for a single, authoritative list of literary works, then certainly for stable and permanent data sets" (Bode 2020: 101). Corpora and algorithms proliferate when models cease to be regarded as "mimetic representations of the world" (Piper 2017: 652; see also Piper 2018: 11, 19) or "summaries or reports about data" and become "mechanisms with which individuals reason and think" (So 2017: 670; cf. Bode 2020: 100). What is meant by this? "Rather than see the model as a potential antagonist, an entity that has brought forth intractable empirical truths that one must accept or reject, the reader is encouraged to reason with the model and its maker to better grasp the data" (So 2017: 671). Corpus designs and algorithms become objectified thoughts, literally intersubjective ideas of sorts (Piper 2017: 656–57), having assumed the form of graphs and formulae. Characteristically, even those most Nietzschean or anarchist approaches to data exploration and corpus design adhere to the simple truth that whatever one does – and a quantum of subjectivism is ineliminable – one should clearly state what one is doing.

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Weatherby (2020) sees the issue of exploration in its relation to modelling and representation in a more nuanced way, which explains why there is so much confusion as to the two approaches: “The sign shift in the computational process occurs on a spectrum that data scientists place between interpretability and predictive accuracy. The former can be sacrificed, as Leo Breiman has shown, in favor of the latter. To model data is to experiment with the relationship of statistical distribution to domain. With the rise of what Breiman calls ‘algorithmic’ techniques – the most widespread of which is now the neural net – the relationship is reversed. Nets are able to meet fit requirements without models (or with generalized models that ‘learn’ as data scientists adjust their parameters), which means that the picture of the structure that allows the data to give good answers is ‘hidden’ in the algorithm, usually called the layers (vectors, or lists of numbers). To my eye, CLS relies largely on model-based techniques while often employing the discovery logic of algorithmic ones in its interpretive efforts, a way of loosening the somewhat mechanical aspects of model-based approaches. This hybrid approach is one of the more interesting aspects of CLS, which may well begin to take more advantage of machine learning in the near future” (Weatherby 2020: 893–894).

We consider Long and So’s haiku classifier, employed with a view to say substantial truths about literary Modernism, a case in point of what Weatherby calls the hybrid approach.

3.4. Use Case: Collecting the Haiku

While Long and So do not devote much attention to the question of compiling a collection on which to train a classifier, we decided to tackle the issue of finding the haiku in the present-day data landscape.

Long and So (2016: 252) formulate their intention: “we want to know whether the machine recognizes a haiku over and against a text that is nonhaiku and, if so, what statistical evidence it uses to make that decision.” To this end, they created two different corpora containing the haiku and the nonhaiku, respectively. As for the eligibility criteria or rather criterion: the haiku corpus contains texts that were labelled as haiku – either

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translations or adaptations. This fact implies the importance of paratextual attributions and metadata. The classifier is then trained to recognize haiku and applied to large test sets with an unknown content.

Now, we asked ourselves what it takes to compile a corpus of the haiku in the data landscape of today.

To all appearances, the haiku as a well-established and strictly prescribed short form should be easy to identify in multi-genre and multilingual collections. Yet difficulties arise due to both cultural (Hokenson 2007; Johnson 2011; Śniecikowska 2016) and infrastructural factors. Given the stringent rules of application for Japanese phonetics (mora,¹² kireji¹³), syntax, and semantics (kigo¹⁴), the genre of the haiku appears to be untranslatable into European literary systems. All European haikus are merely approximations of the precise form contingent on the specific structure of the Japanese language. This impossibility of identifying the canonical version of the haiku outside Japanese literature, paired with the heterogeneity of the existing infrastructure of text collections, makes the search for sustainable data extremely time and resource consuming. The following questions arise:

Which features of different European approaches to the strict Japanese genre should be given priority in identifying a poem as a haiku?

How can the evaluation and exploration of literary text collections be facilitated in regard to these features?

To answer these questions, a selection of corpora¹⁵ from a list of literary resources (collected and curated since the beginning of the CLS INFRA project as part of deliverable 6.1) was chosen for closer examination.

Relying on metadata- and data-derived information, the corpora were scanned for both “explicit” and “implicit” realizations.

¹² A unit of duration in Japanese used to measure the length of words and utterances; mora languages differ from syllable languages like English.

¹³ Cutting syllable, separating the first verse from the others.

¹⁴ Codified signals of seasons: over 1000 lexemes contained in the *saijiki*, a prescriptive list of such words.

¹⁵ The history of our searches is provisionally stored in Gitlab (please note that access at this time is limited to CLS INFRA project members): <https://gitlab.clsinfra.io:11435/cls-infra/haiku-challenge>; <https://gitlab.clsinfra.io:11435/cls-infra/haiku-challenge/-/issues>.

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Explicit haikus are either translations of the Japanese models or original creations labelled as “haiku”. Their findability relies heavily on metadata provided by corpus compilers/distributors. Two telling cases are Wikisource¹⁶ and the Russian National Corpus,¹⁷ which recognize the haiku as a distinct form, but only in annotations to individual poems and not in the inventory of genres.

As for implicit haikus, their findability depends on the addressability of certain textual features (such as: verses, syllables, and topics) ensuing from the structure of a corpus.

For example: As a result of favouring the cultural universal of verse count over the relation to the number of syllables (absent in Japanese, instead divisible into morae), an algorithm was devised that extracts three-verse poems from the DLK (German Poetry Corpus; cf. Haider 2021). In the DLK, syllables are already marked up, which makes counting syllables possible and thus provides an additional criterion to identify possible haikus. However, the ideal structure of 17 (5+7+5) syllables could not be identified.

Two problems arise: inconsistencies in the recording of metadata and discrepancies in the structural annotation of texts in literary corpora.

Based on implementation concepts being developed within the CLS INFRA project, the following solution is proposed for the aforementioned problems: firstly, a descriptive metamodel for poetry corpora will be introduced which is derived from the “Metamodel for Corpus Metadata” (MCM; Odebrecht 2018), allowing a fine-grained genre-specific description of collections. Secondly, a machine-readable archive will be provided which contains the results of previous searches for particular poetry forms; it will contain explicit statements about various features of the corpus (e.g. whether a certain method yielded positive results).

The metamodel will be realized as an extension to CIDOC CRM,¹⁸ using other well-established ontologies, e.g. FRBRoo.¹⁹ The class “Annotation” of the MCM will be

¹⁶ https://wikisource.org/wiki/Main_Page.

¹⁷ <https://ruscorpora.ru/new/search-poetic.html>.

¹⁸ <https://cidoc-crm.org/>.

¹⁹ <https://cidoc-crm.org/frbroo/home-0>.

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introduced to CIDOC CRM's event-centred model to record various features of corpora including provenance information. This allows the expression of even conflicting statements about a resource, which can thereby be traced back and assessed individually. In the haiku example, this approach will be tested by attaching information to corpora such as tokenization rules, syllable structure, verse structure, etc. By linking concepts to external reference resources, e.g. Wikidata, it will be possible to search for literary studies' notions used in the annotation of documents in the corpus.

4. Corpus Design: Methods of Selection and Sampling (Use Case: The Slovak Novel)

In the previous chapter, we described how CLS adopts the working methods of corpus linguistics and NLP: collective effort guided by standardized workflows, which divide the general task into a number of smaller well-defined steps. One of the most characteristic features is the clear separation of the phases of corpus building and the exploration thereof.

What sets apart Computational Literary Studies and the data driven humanities in general from the qualitative or hermeneutic approaches is firstly that the difference between a population and a sample as well as selection criteria are made explicit (Piper in progress, Preface; Piper 2017). Every researcher has a model of his or her object; CLS is all about making the model explicit. Secondly, the "explication" of the model takes on the form of a machine-readable corpus. As Michel Piotrowski stated in a lecture: "When we look for epistemological differences between 'traditional' and digital humanities, machine-readable corpora stand out" (Piotrowski 2022: 6)

Among all disciplines of "traditional" humanities, the reader of literary studies' papers becomes especially rarely if ever acquainted with the motivation behind the choice of texts from a larger pool and their arrangement in a corpus; the texts are quoted as authoritative or telling examples rather than organized in elaborated ensembles which are supposed to yield reliable and reproducible results.

Literary scholars think in anthologies rather than in corpora. Larger historical syntheses are underpinned by the tacit assumption that the findings or the interpretations

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bear on the whole population so that neither the relation of the sample to the population nor the criteria for the selection thereof are stated. While the researchers in CLS perceive corpus-building and the process of its examination as both conceptually distinct and separated in time, in qualitative literary studies “corpus building” typically coincides with the moment of research, i.e. taking excerpts from primary and secondary literature. While traditional literary studies values the force of insight that convinces the reader to accept the conclusions arrived at by a researcher, CLS attaches the highest importance to the reproducibility of the results (Piper 2020), hence the emphasis on the accessibility of data along with the explicit character of their selection. Both values are intertwined – the more specific the documentation and the more transparent the structure of a collection, the greater its accessibility for the other members of the CLS community.

Yet the explicit criteria for the selection and the arrangement of texts pertain to the “theories of data and domain that cannot be datafied themselves” (Weatherby 2020: 899). Moreover, these explicit theories vary widely as they justify countless possible research questions. Given an infinite number of vantage points on pools and samples, data, and domains, “the modeling process entails a tremendous amount of subjectivity. But the process is not arbitrary” (Piper 2017: 656). The ethos of this corpus-based discipline suggests that all choices should be clearly stated and documented in relation to the research goals. According to the best practices (such as the FAIR principles), codes and data are published in a way that makes them findable and accessible and reusable, be it in the process of reproducing research or be it to use the data to create one’s own research corpus.

This chapter focuses on the theories of selection and sampling – understood as the translatability of quality into quantity (and *vice versa*) – as well as practices which these theories justify or motivate; “this is an area prone to paradox, where even the apparently simplest decisions can have extensive ramifications” (Hunston 2008: 154). We aim to explore conceptual rather than technical conditions of access to textual data. Our perspective on the vast field has its vanishing point in the enhancing of findability and accessibility of collections and texts bearing certain qualities so as to facilitate building

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new research corpora (reusability). How can one provide guidance in the awe-inspiring chaos of online literary collections? An answer to this question is offered by our original typology of literary text collections drawing upon the most widely acknowledged theories of linguistic corpora (section 4.1). Further on we ask: According to which key considerations are corpora structured; what features make them easier to find and reuse? What metadata do they bring along? How can information be technically retrieved from them?

We relate the technical question to our use case: the project of constructing a corpus of the Slovak novel guided by the ELTeC principles. The work on the corpus brings to light the fragmentary character of the present-day data landscape in terms of both technical accessibility of resources which have fallen out of the scope of world literature's canon (including inadequate metadata) and cultural contingencies undermining our notions of eligibility, representativeness, and balance.

4.1. Typology of Corpora According to Their Purpose

Regarding the content of a collection, it is best to sort resources according to the purpose for which they were compiled. In doing so, we depart from the usual linguistic considerations focusing on the size and the mediality of gathered documents (recordings, manuscripts, etc.; cf. Hundt 2008; Wichmann 2008; Allwood 2008; Ädel 2020). The latter criterion is superfluous because of CLS's almost exclusive concentration on text in the graphemic form (see chapter 3).

We propose distinguishing the following kinds of collections: general-purpose collections, (parts of) reference corpora, monitor corpora, opportunistic corpora, digital critical editions, and research corpora. This breakdown clearly cannot be seen as a classification because the criteria are neither exclusive nor exhaustive; rather we strive to recognise characteristic types so as to expedite the navigation among textual collections. The ordering of corpora according to their *teloi* is not at variance with our value-neutral approach; on the contrary, we believe the application of a corpus to be sufficient explanation of its construction: "It is a truism that there is no such thing as a

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‘good’ or a ‘bad’ corpus, because how a corpus is designed depends on what kind of corpus it is and how it is going to be used” (Hunston 2008: 156).

4.1.1. General-Purpose Collections

This segment concerns such collections as Project Gutenberg, Europeana, HathiTrust Digital Library, Internet Archive, Google Books, or Wiki Source. In addition, resources made available by libraries belong in this category.

In the case of the Slovak novel, the compiler of the corpus can refer to a couple of high-quality general-purpose collections, such as the digital collections of the Slovak National Library (<https://dikda.eu/>) and the University Library in Bratislava (<http://digitalna.kniznica.info/browse>), both affiliated with Europeana, and the collection of the Slovak classics in HTML and rtf provided by the SME daily (<https://zlatyfond.sme.sk/autori#U>). Of course, there is also the Slovak Wikisource (https://sk.wikisource.org/wiki/Wikizdroje:Hlavn%C3%A1_str%C3%A1nka).

General-purpose collections were envisioned as, on the one hand, gigantic libraries overcoming all limitations of availability of texts for close reading purposes. On the other hand, many of them were interlaced from the outset with research on big data (Google Books’ Ngram Viewer, HathiTrust Research Center, etc.). Under the circumstances, general-purpose collections offer not only the largest number of textual artifacts in the largest number of languages but also the largest number of formats. Scans of pages are intended for human readers, and since human students of literature must quote, the images of pages have undergone optical character recognition (OCR) to make their textual content selectable and copyable (sometimes in the Page XML format, like in Europeana); plain text or JSON, which conform to machine-readability, are also made available. The format of the texts becomes an issue because these collections typically serve as a resource drawn upon in order to create research corpora. One can hardly harvest photographs and OCR has varying levels of reliability.

Thomas Padilla (2016) distinguishes among the providers of downloadable or at least explorable collections between 1. Content Steward Websites; 2. Content Steward

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Repositories; and 3. Community Repositories. In the first case, one can simply download the collection from a website, while the latter two make use of repository collection software (APIs); the difference between a Content Steward Repository and a Community Repository boils down to the fact that a Community Repository hosts collections that it does not own (Github, HathiTrust, Digital Public Library of America, LAUDATIO).

The researcher is not always left to their own devices when mining for texts in general-purpose collections. The HathiTrust Research Center established in cooperation with Indiana University and the University of Illinois (<https://www.hathitrust.org/htrc>) provides researchers not only with a suite of off-the-shelf appliances, such as algorithms, visualization tools, and HTRC Extracted Features (an open, large-scale dataset of content pulled from over 15 million volumes), but also with the possibility to create bespoke “worksets” or research corpora (user-created collections of HathiTrust volumes with export possibilities, selected for example on the basis of a genre or gender). Affiliation with a HathiTrust member institution is not required when a researcher wants to use the tools.

From the perspective of corpus linguistics, the general-purpose collections appear as “text databases” rather than as corpora in the strict sense, the latter being characterized as “principled or structured” and customarily annotated compilations of texts (Kennedy 1998: 3; Hundt 2008: 170). General purpose collections stand out through the great number of texts and languages covered: Archive.org recognizes 3654 names of languages (in the cases of Wikisource and Google Books, the number is greater than 100).

While some linguists acknowledge the Internet as a kind of maximum range corpus (Hassel 2001; Meyer et al. 2003), CLS’s identity depends on staying within the limits of the literary, whatever this notion may mean (see chapter 3). Accordingly, the CLS researcher scrutinizes specific collections whose elements are described in metadata or annotations as literary. Therefore, the question of the documentation of this kind of collection is gaining in importance.

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4.1.2. Reference Corpora (Subcorpora of)

This segment concerns such collections as the Polish National Corpus or DeReKo (Deutsches Referenzkorpus).

In linguistics, reference corpora are “designed to investigate a given language as a whole” (Hunston 2008: 154). Because of this aspiration, they usually contain subcorpora of literary texts, as the language of literature (fiction or poetry) is considered to be one of the major registers, sufficiently diverse from other situational ways of using a language. For example, Biber et al. (1999: 15) distinguish four registers of the English language, including fiction alongside dialogue (conversation), news, and academic prose.

The designs of reference corpora vary considerably, they are just as diverse as the needs of corpus linguists are, ranging from a folder containing text files to advanced search architectures, such as COMMAS II, which is suitable for complex multilayer linguistic corpora with diverse types of annotation. One important and in many cases unfortunate feature of the state-of-the-art corpora is that they limit access to the texts themselves, which is mostly due to copyright issues (see chapter 5). The researcher is oftentimes allowed to build his or her subcorpus in the framework of the reference corpus, a process usually based on metadata concerning, for example, the genre of the period of selected texts.

For the researchers of CLS, it is vital to remember that the linguistic definition of the register of literary language may differ substantially from the literary scholarship’s usual understanding of literariness. Linguistic registers are distinguished based on situational and institutional rather than qualitative or essential characteristics: “Publishers, libraries, and university courses all contribute to defining what works are regarded as literature” (Mahlberg 2015: 348). The register approach to the text varieties differs from genre and style perspectives (Biber and Conrad 2009; Mahlberg 2015: 348). While the genre approach typically requires access to complete texts, register and style studies, focusing on frequent features, can work with text samples. More importantly, a register is defined as an author’s attitude towards language, whereas the focus on styles and genres relates an utterance to a literary system following its particular laws of evolution,

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irreducible to the history of language. Interestingly, classical Structuralism endeavoured to relate a literary utterance both to the system of language and to the system of literary history (Sławiński 2001). In some, mostly phenomenological, approaches, aesthetic factors, i.e. ones connected with the subjective reaction to forms, exceed the scope of the theories of literary register or linguistic styles.

The Slovak National Corpus uses “fiction” only as one ingredient (alongside the journalistic and the professional registers) to balance the manually morphologically annotated corpus r-mak (different proportions hold in different versions, always oscillating around 50% fictional texts). The subcorpus of “fiction texts” of prim-9.0-public-img – a monolingual corpus, comprised of all texts published or written after the year 1955 – contains 263 million tokens. The corpus is queried with the help of off-the-shelf interfaces.

4.1.3. Digital Critical Editions

This segment concerns such collections as Electronic Beowulf (ed. Kevin Kiernan <http://ebeowulf.uky.edu/>), Critical Editions of the New Testament Online (ed. David C. Parker, <https://primarysources.brillonline.com/browse/critical-editions-of-the-new-testament-online>), or Perseus Digital Library (<http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/>). A leading representative of such an exhaustive project is Anne Bohnenkamp-Renken, Silke Henke, and Fotis Jannidis’s historico-critical edition of Goethe’s *Faust*: <http://www.faustedition.net/>.

The following exclusively describes open-source critical editions that are scholarly projects in their own right. Moreover, scholarly editing – as most notably stated by Katherine Bode (2018: 17–58) – can constitute a rival paradigm to mainstream CLS, pursuing mostly a statistical approach. According to Bode, Moretti’s “distant reading” simply amplifies close reading in that it treats texts as fixed entities, pinpointed to the moment of their first publication, while ignoring both the intrinsic development of texts and their alternating reception history. In both processes, larger societal forces are at work shaping the fields wherein authors and readers act. The practical effect of these reflections can be appraised at: <https://cdhrdatasys.anu.edu.au/tobecontinued/>.

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Perceived as resources to draw upon,²⁰ critical editions are admittedly easy to find and access, offering texts of high quality; however, their conceptual strengths, materialized in the philological apparatus, can pose obstacles when compiling one's own research corpus. (Moreover, there are issues of copyright so that these remarks concern exclusively digital critical editions with clear and machine readable licensing/reuse conditions.²¹) The well-established basic form of a critical edition consists of parts that must be stripped away before the exploration or the modelling of the textual data can even begin, such as an introduction which lays out the history of the text and bibliography, a table of symbols used in the critical apparatus, appendices, and indices. The most advanced editions assemble numerous versions, at times all existing versions of the text, which makes the harvesting of a text cumbersome, if possible at all.

In March 2022, German scholars put out a manifesto of digital editions describing the best practices of such enterprises: <https://dhd-blog.org/?p=17563>.

We haven't come across a Slovak edition that would meet these high standards.

4.1.4. Monitor Corpora

This segment concerns such collections as DraCor, ELTeC, TextGrid, or Deutsches Textarchiv.

With a view to our research case, Marek Debnár of the University of Nitra is conducting a project the result of which should be a comprehensively annotated full-text digital collection of Slovak prose up to 1951. The collection will be processed and annotated according to the ELTeC standards.

In linguistics, monitor corpora are designed to monitor the dynamic reality of a language in real time (McEnery, Xiao and Tono 2006: 67–69), which implies a high level of curation. Analogously, the monitor corpora for CLS can be described as principled

²⁰ This is not an uncontested view: Boot and van Zundert (2011) propose treating digital editions as services and not resources.

²¹ <http://sites.tufts.edu/perseusupdates/2015/03/04/getting-to-open-data-for-classical-greek-and-latin-breaking-old-habits-and-undoing-the-damage-a-call-for-comment/>.

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collections of whole texts that were selected and assembled in a balanced way with a view to enabling research; they are, furthermore, continuously curated.

These corpora combine providing access to text files (in TEI XML, JSON, txt, etc.) with extensive documentation including license info, PIDs, and tools serving exploring and visualization purposes.

As opposed to general-purpose collections (Wikisource, HathiTrust, Archive.org, Europeana), monitor corpora have a well-defined scope and limit themselves to one genre (novel, drama) or one author (Shakespeare, Calderon).

High quality resources, such as ELTeC or DraCor, compare the realizations of one genre in different languages and thus foster and facilitate comparative approaches. However, many resources characterized by a substantial curatorial effort – like TextGrid or Deutsches Textarchiv – limit themselves to one language.

4.1.5. Corpora Compiled on the Basis of a Research Question

This segment concerns corpora that have been used to address specific research questions and subsequently stored in GitHub or GitLab, Zenodo, LAUDATIO and other subject-specific repositories in order to make the replication of research possible.

These kinds of corpora are most likely to meet the expectations of CLS researchers as they usually are ingeniously constructed and comprehensively described (including CC license, PID, “cite as” info, etc.), while the data they contain are normalized. However, they usually consist of texts balanced with regard to specific research questions. Thus they are suitable for replicating the research in the context of which they arose, but new research calls for assembling a new corpus or at least thoroughly modifying an already existing one.

4.1.6. Opportunistic Corpora

One of the most perplexing problems regarding the findability and accessibility of corpora inheres within the distinction between opportunistic and principled corpora. An opportunistic corpus is said to “represent nothing more nor less than the data that it was

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possible to gather for a specific task” (McEnery and Hardie 2012: 11). An opportunistic corpus seems, on the one hand, to achieve the maximally economical approach that motivates this review. On the other hand, forgoing the ideal of adhering to a precise sampling frame in favour of what is easily findable and reusable may affect the quality of research (cf. Edmond 2015). The key principles of CLS, such as expanding or surpassing the canonical, can also be compromised. Many a computational contribution compiles its corpora using exclusively canonical texts (such as the ZEIT Library of 100 Books, ed. by Raddatz 2009), by which they often inadvertently reproduce a normative-evaluative perspective on literature reinforced by the limited spread of attention in qualitative literary studies that are able to consider a much smaller number of texts (cf. Herrmann and Lauer 2018: 135).

“It is, however, very difficult not to include some element of opportunism in corpus design, as we do not have boundless resources” (Ädel 2020: 6) – and the aim of the present review consists not in discouraging researchers from replicating or using opportunistic corpora, but, again, in recommending being explicit about their choices. Moreover, not all biases and stereotypes reproduced by opportunistic corpora are simply false but, conversely, may be illuminating. Algee-Hewitt and colleagues (cf. Algee-Hewitt 2016; Liddle 2019) found that the texts contained in the collection of canonical novels score much lower on the scale of informational redundancy in comparison to the representatives of a general population. The higher information density in the canon in relation to the archive discloses important forces at work in the processes of literary history. Though, to achieve this engaging result one must compare an opportunistic (or canonical) corpus with an archive, transcending the group of the most easily accessible texts.

4.2. Key Considerations for Selection and Sampling (Relative to Different Types of Corpora, e.g. Exploratory or Modelling)

Most of what will be said below about the key considerations regarding the architecture of text collection refers to the categories worked out in the framework of the modelling

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approach in contradistinction to exploration (see section 3.3); even the daunting data explorers speak in the language of modelling by referring to representation, balance, and eligibility. However, the names of the customary features acquire in the exploratory approach a new meaning which so far has not found a clear explanation.

The considerations outlined in this section likewise lean, as in the previous one, on corpus linguistics. As Paul Rayson puts it: “The corpus research process involves three main stages: corpus compilation, annotation, and retrieval” (Rayson 2015: 33). Since we examine the intellectual access to data, we consider in this section only the first stage of corpus compilation according to Kennedy (1998: 70), i.e. corpus design, leaving aside the technical issues of text capture and text encoding (Rayson 2015: 35; cf. Adolphs 2008: 21; McEnery and Hardie 2012: 241; Meyer 2002: 55–80; O’Keeffe and McCarthy 2010; Reppen 2010).

We also appropriate from linguistics the three main features of a reliable research text corpus, i.e. completeness, representativeness, and proportion (balance); the hierarchy of these notions alongside their precise meaning in a given context depend on the research goal pursued by the compiler. “The notions of representativeness and balance are scalar and vague” (Ädel 2020: 5).

The compiler’s tragedy – as we would like to call this coercion to freely choose – consists in the fact that no corpus can satisfy all demands as they contradict one another. One must choose between positive values. While representativeness directly contradicts completeness, balance and representativeness often correspond to different approaches to research material, even though they entail one another. You cannot conceive of a representative corpus without a proper proportion of its constituents, while the parts to be balanced are defined on the basis of what they represent outside the corpus. However, principally one has to pick only one. For example, the multi-language monitor corpus European Literary Text Collection (ELTeC) introduces a fixed proportion of women writers in relation to the whole sample. By doing this, the compilers sacrifice the direct representation of a given national literature, where women could have played varied roles, in favour of balance, which, for its part, buttresses comparativeness and variance.

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Another case of bolstering balance at the cost of representation concerns not transcultural comparisons but one language in its historical development: “Balancing decisions could even be based on comparability with some other corpus: for example, in a diachronic corpus of English [...], fiction writing may be deliberately overrepresented and religious writing underrepresented in earlier periods to allow for easier comparison to present-day English” (Ädel 2020: 5).

In the compiler’s tragedy, like in its Greek predecessor, there is one fundamental value all characters abide by: transparency. The hero is a hero by virtue of taking responsibility for all choices.

The conflict between representativeness and balancing becomes particularly grave in our use case of the corpus of the Slovak novel, which should be compatible with the principles of ELTeC. The political and cultural history of Slovakia puts into sharp relief the problems of eligibility, the paradoxes of representativeness, as well as the tension between representativeness and balance or – to be precise – the fact that the apparently arbitrary balance of ELTeC is more adaptable to some literary cultures – e.g. English, German, or French – than to others, as if it represents their cultural dominance even though it was designed bearing equity in mind.

4.2.1. Corpus Architecture / Composition (Size, Eligibility, Structuring of Texts and Annotations, Entity Typing)

Before we address the question of the regulative principles of corpus composition, an explanation is in order concerning the notion of corpus composition or corpus architecture. In linguistics, “[c]orpus architecture refers to the set of design decisions taken in the conceptual division and interrelations of types of objects contained in a corpus, such as texts, annotations and metadata, and the ways in which we choose to represent these” (Zeldes 2020: 49). The compiler’s decisions concern, among other things, what kind of text is eligible for a corpus or a subcorpus (which features are crucial for its membership in a genre or a type) and the texts’ arrangement in subcorpora, which themselves can contain further subcorpora.

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Eligibility is exactly the moment of passage from qualitative analysis that establishes classes to the quantitative research on those classes. Take the example of the Slovak novel. The novel being a protean phenomenon in all quarters, the history of Slovak culture – centuries of political dependency and religious strife – makes the decision as to the novelistic character of a piece of narrative prose all the more problematic. Hungarian and Austrian oppression – as every oppression hindering realism in favour of messianic and magical thinking – alongside the rural character of the country, which was devoid of metropolises, where the Western novel thrived, impacted the poetics of narrative prose. The dominant tendency of this fiction is its fabulous character, magical realism *avant la lettre*, leaning on folklore, or the mythicization of the past in the historical novel. How liberal is the notion of the novel between 1840 and 1920? The modern Slovak language was only codified in 1843, after the Protestants lost faith in a satisfying agreement with their Czech coreligionists and reached out to the Slovak Catholics; it took ten more years to agree on an orthography (a factor even gaining prominence in machine-readable corpora). Moreover, Slovak literary history encompasses novels written in Latin and neighbouring languages throughout the nineteenth century. Should the corpus compiler favour linguistic or geographical or morphological criteria?

As for the corpus architecture in the narrow sense of the word, “[a] minimal corpus macro-structure is [...] a single or ‘top-level’ corpus object, directly containing the ‘pieces’, which can be referred to as ‘documents’” (Zeldes 2020: 50). In a CLS project, because of its classifier-induced essentialism (see section 3.1), a corpus can typically consist of two subcorpora – one which comprises the class in question and another serving as a backdrop, a control group, or an archive. The most frequent types of linguistic annotations are (1) part-of-speech (POS) tagging, (2) lemmatization, (3) syntactic parsing, and (4) semantic annotation (Newman and Cox 2020: 25). In CLS, a special kind of semantic annotation appears to be very useful: entity typing, which consists in assigning types – such as institution, person, location, or period – to mentions of entities in documents. There are also attempts at introducing specifically literary annotation, for example the annotation of literary levels (Gius, Reiter and Willand 2019).

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It is fortunate that in such an intricate and contentious field as literary studies, with texts demonstrating potentially endless multidimensionality, the researcher has recourse to the standard of nested annotation (ISO 24612): “Some data models allow us to attach annotations only to nodes, or also to edges; some data models even allow annotations of annotations (e.g. Dipper 2005), which opens up the possibility of annotation sub-graphs expressing, for example, provenance (i.e. who or what created an annotation and when, see Eckart de Castilho et al. 2017) or certainty of annotations (e.g. an ‘uncertain’ label, or numerical likelihood estimate of annotation accuracy). Another annotation model constraint is whether multiple instances of the same annotation in the same position are allowed (e.g. conflicting versions of the same annotation [...], see Kountz et al. 2008)” (Zeldes 2020: 57). Nested annotations or, specifically, annotating metadata make up part of the solution we advocate in chapter three, where we describe our problems with collecting haikus across national literatures and propose a solution: a tool that makes possible the annotation of an annotation.

4.2.2. Completeness

Completeness is relative to the architectural decisions concerning the scope of the corpus. This feature is usually dependent more on fortuitous facts of history than on deliberate selection. A complete corpus routinely comprises all texts of a given cultural formation – such as Attic tragedy or the pre-Socratic philosophers or Marcel Proust’s writings – that have been handed down to our times in their entirety or only as fragments. Collections that pertain to cultures distant in time can be deemed complete by virtue of their being fragmentary. Mike Kestemont and colleagues used a statistical model from ecology, originally relating to extinct species, to assess how much literature from the Middle Ages has been lost to us (Kestemont et al. 2022). Additionally, collections of texts by one author or by a few writers, e.g. constituting a group or a circle, qualify for being called complete. In all cases, the question arises regarding against what backdrop the features of a complete collection can become discernible and measurable. The limits of the documented whole hinge on the research question.

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With regard to the Slovak novel, extreme hardship endured by authors belonging to the officially unrecognized and relatively small nation may explain why we have so far been able to harvest no more than forty-four novelistic texts. Under these conditions, reaching the threshold of one hundred novels could mean striving for completeness rather than a representative – let alone a well-balanced – corpus.

4.2.3. Representativeness

The collections that are incomplete in the sense that they comprise only samples of a bigger pool can represent a population of language users (e.g. fiction writers or poets), a language variety (e.g. verse language vs. prose), or a type of discourse (e.g. realist novel or Avant-garde poetry) (Ädel 2020: 4). On the most general level, the representativeness of a sample matches its capacity to be the basis of indicative reasoning; a sample is representative when “findings from the sample can be generalised to the population” (McEnery and Hardie 2012: 250).

According to the prescriptive view on representativeness – the one complying with modelling in contradistinction to exploration (see section 3.3) – the population should be depicted in its entire complexity insofar as features accounted for remain relevant to the research question driving the assembling of a corpus: “Representativeness refers to the extent to which a sample includes the full range of variability in a population” (Biber 1993: 243). Furthermore, the size of the sample should according to this approach be proportional to the scope of the population (Ädel 2020: 4). We come across another paradox, as only a complete collection can represent or simply have the whole variety of features of a population. A complete sample cannot, nevertheless, have the feature of representativeness because to represent something entails being different from the represented. Especially in the case of fiction and poetry, we cannot claim to know the probed population, while previous knowledge of the whole population is required to achieve a “probability sample”, where every feature or entity belonging to the population has an equal prospect of being sampled.²² The literary researcher has no access to even

²² <https://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=2134>

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as modest a benchmark as an exhaustive list of texts published let alone written in a given land in a given period. Even the records of national libraries, which are not necessarily fully reliable, vary from case to case, hindering transcultural comparisons: the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (established 1666) precedes the Library of Congress (1800), while the Deutsche Nationalbibliothek seems to be their junior partner (established in 1913; cf. Herrmann and Lauer 2018: 137).

Consequently, statistical methods in CLS are limited to descriptive statistics; inferential statistics, which generalizes patterns from a sample to an entire population, is illegitimate by default or, in the best case scenario, should be taken with a pinch of salt; hence the attractiveness of the exploratory approach at the expense of the methodically doubtful modelling approach (see section 3.3.).

One can speak about representativeness – and completeness as well – only with regard to a specific research question or – as Herrmann und Lauer put it (2018: 138) – “only from a certain perspective”. Perspectivity entails, however, difference and even competition. It is as though a sample cannot be reliable without being partisan or tendentious. As such, the perspectivity of representative sampling corresponds to the political dimension of representation (see biases 4.2.5).

With fewer than 50 Slovak novels available online at the moment, it is hard to speak of a representative sample of a population.

4.2.4. Proportion (Balance)

“The representativeness of a corpus [...] depends primarily upon how balanced the corpus is” (Xia 2014: 38). “Balance” is a mathematically well-defined representation of what in informal language is called the proportion of texts in a collection. The internal composition of the corpus can be understood as the proportions of the subcorpora or subsections of which it is made up (Hunston 2008: 163). In a balanced corpus, “the relative sizes of each of [the subsections] have been chosen with the aim of adequately representing the range of language that exists in the population of texts being sampled” (McEnery and Hardie 2012: 239). The same goes for the varieties of literary utterances.

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The quality of being balanced bears on the relations between different components of a corpus rather than the relation between the corpus and linguistic or literary reality, as is the case with representativeness. Balance is, on the one hand, indispensable with regard to representativeness, pursuing the regulative idea of “probability sample”, yet it has its own qualities, irreducible to the pool. While the representativeness corresponds rather to the modelling approach, balance accords more with exploration, although there are no absolutes in this situation of paradox.

Our intended corpus of the Slovak novel lays bare hegemonic assumptions hidden behind the ostensibly neutral, even intentionally progressive demands of ELTeC, which for the sake of comparability of different national corpora gives preference to proportion in relation to representativeness. However, the criteria the compilers strive to meet shed some light on the irreflexive self-reliance of the established *Kulturnationen*. It is obvious that the distribution of Slovak novels will be shifted on the time axis as is the case with the proportion of women writers. The difficult conditions under which Slovak literati worked answer for the over-representation of clergymen, under-representation of women, and the virtual impossibility of meeting the condition that only 10% of writers be represented by three works. In our case, a few authors, having secured their livelihood with the help of the Christian churches, produced relatively many prosaic texts, potential novels.

4.2.5. Frequent Biases

Biases can influence the perception of eligibility as well as endanger the representativeness and proportion of corpora.

Their effects can be aggravated by various factors, including the geographical location of the compiler (Rastogi, Nagappan and Gousios 2016). Not only are we limited in space, but also in time as, for example, the copyright often compels a focus on older literature (see chapter 5). Numerous authors raise the issue of the survivorship of data, which occurs when only the data that have undergone a previous selection process are accounted for rather than a comprehensive image of a target population. Such is the case

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with data generated by corporations or state archives, which both as a rule select data according to their agendas, oftentimes suppressing uncomfortable truths, and restrict access to some data sets or to the algorithms that produce the data sets in question.

The technical and political biases are often said to be entangled to the point of indistinguishability. The very technological methods of avoiding biases may reproduce them on another plane. Even the apparently purely scientific ways of achieving representativeness involve decisions that are isomorphic with the inception of political inequalities: “One of the ways of selecting material for a [representative] corpus is by stratified sampling, where the hierarchical structure (or ‘strata’) of the population is determined in advance” (Ädel 2020: 4).

The political aspect of corpus representativeness can be exemplified by the discussion in the triangle Franco Moretti, Ted Underwood, and Katherine Bode: Moretti (2005) relates literary Big Data to the canon wars waged at the time in the name of inclusivity; the promise of Big Data lies in expanding the scope of represented perspectives (see chapter 3). Underwood (2019) suggests that Moretti’s framing of his in fact exploratory research was just a tactical move. Rather than pursuing the equity of representation, one should concentrate on the exploration of data for the exploration’s sake (see above in section 3.3) and thus emancipate computation from the shackles of political calculation. Bode (2020) argues that exactly the seemingly ideology-free approach is the epitome of ideology as the naturalization of the status quo. In other words, the question of ideology pertains to the sampling criteria, particularly representativeness. According to Bode, the political discussion boils down to the “disagreement [...] between [...] those who maintain that literary insight depends on critically analyzing and historicizing data sets prior to statistical analysis of patterns and trends, and those who claim that statistical analysis, in the absence of or with minimal investigation and contextualization of data sets, is sufficient for critical and historical understanding” (Bode 2020: 95).

Bode advances the idea that the construction of a collection should map the construction of the social literary field; otherwise it runs the risk of simply reinforcing

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ideological illusions: “the literary work is an idea shored up by substantial historical, cultural, social, legal, political, institutional, and other practices, conventions, and discourses, whereas the literary system has simply been scholarly shorthand for the operations of these practices, conventions, and discourses in particular times and places. Now that digital resources and methods suggest possibilities for investigating rather than simply invoking this broader phenomenon, we face the challenge of determining what vast and distributed network of specific material objects to include in such investigations” (Bode 2020: 99). The meaning of representativeness changes in this context. According to its new meaning, the researcher models the forces of exclusion and stratification rather than their effects alone. Some selection biases – Bode claims (2020: 109) – operate at the level of the population, such as exclusion bias and sampling bias (the former relates to taking into consideration exclusively bearers of certain features such as people using landline phones in 1934 or 2022, while the latter pertains to the questions one asks).

4.3. Data Formats

A topical guide to data formats in the Digital Humanities can be found under this address: <https://guides.library.ucla.edu/c.php?g=180580&p=1186565>; the list was the point of reference for D3.1 in the part concerning data formats.

Data formats evolve rapidly and at different rates, therefore this subsection looks ahead to the shortest shelf life. Needless to say, different formats suit different needs and, tautologically, different research designs demand different formats.

One can represent the landscape of data formats regarded from the point of view of CLS as a broad field delimited by two poles: plain text and image. Leaving aside narrative research on films and images, our report focuses on the textual side. General-purpose collections offer in their capacity as vast libraries the images of books, while at the same time providing access to plain text, usually via the OCR of the scanned books. As plain text remains the most easily readable for machines (and is, as D3.1 showed, the most popular among researchers), specific research questions entail pre-structuring textual material in such a way that specific divisions and distinctions are introduced into

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its instances – lines, verses, paragraphs, pages, chapters, etc. The divisions are introduced to a markup or metatext in a series of different ways, allowing for different granularities of divisions and other annotations.

4.4. Metadata's Formats and Structures (Generic vs. Domain-Specific Repositories)

Leading resources on metadata standards are:

<https://fairsharing.org/>

<https://www.forschungsdaten.info/themen/beschreiben-und-dokumentieren/metadaten-und-metadatenstandards/>

Metadata are vital with regard to the findability as well as the accessibility of literary resources because they serve both as labels, informing about the contents of a collection, and to represent the collection's structure. In some cases, for example LAUDATIO (<https://www.laudatio-repository.org/>), they also document workflows that lead to the emergence of a collection: the leading research questions and deliberations concerning representativeness and bias. In this way, the researcher can better assess the reusability of the data for his or her own research.

Most text repositories discussed above provide their users with a possibility to browse through collections according to metadata, beginning with high-level metadata (author, genre) and ending with genre-specific metadata, such as stanzas or meter (e.g. the German Poetry Corpus <https://github.com/tnhaider/DLK> and the subcorpus of the Russian National Corpus <https://ruscorpora.ru/new/search-poetic.html>).

In principle, one can differentiate between generic and domain-specific repositories. In the former case, corresponding to our general-purpose collections, the exploration of the collection is enabled by tags or keywords relating to subject areas and by top-level metadata (title, year, author, license or file extension, etc.). Models for metadata formats are provided by state and university libraries or specialist information services (for example: <https://www.evifa.de/de>, <https://www.historicum.net>). Generic repositories such as <https://zenodo.org/> can be counted among these forms of indexing. They typically enable the browsing of collections with the help of top-level metadata or

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thematic tags or abstracts of the projects. However, in the case of extensive generic collections, different data structures, concepts, and collections may loom behind the same uniform metadata categories. Even some repositories with a domain-specific focus – such as the Linguistic Data Consortium (LDC) or the Oxford Text Archive (OTA) – likewise support generic exploration since only little subject-focused metadata can be used in queries.

All collections of Slovak literature belong to the class of generic repositories. Ironically, the collection richest in novelistic material (the Golden Collection of the SME Daily <https://zlatyfond.sme.sk/autori#U>) has almost no metadata. Often, one has to refer to external sources (handbooks, Wikipedia, etc.) to find out whether the prosaic text is classified as a novel.

Domain-specific catalogs and repositories provide subject-specific metadata for concrete data types: in comparison to generic indexing, domain-specific repositories are typically focused on particular data types, data formats, or subject areas. Repositories such as the Deutsches Textarchiv, the TextGrid repository (Schmunk and Funk 2016), the GAMS (Stigler and Steiner 2018), the Language Resource Catalog of the Open Language Archives Community (OLAC), and LAUDATIO have more extensive subject- and partially data-type-focused metadata. The most specific queries are possible in digital critical editions.

Ted Underwood’s observation that “one of the main problems confronting distant reading is the scarcity of metadata about genre in large digital collections” (Underwood 2014: 2) applies mostly to generic collections. Analogously, archive.org is searchable by following high-level metadata: author, language, availability (with regard to copyright and licensing), year, and topic and subject, but not genre (some are included, inconsistently, in the topic and subject category, e.g. science fiction, American poetry, road fiction, etc.). Texts hailing from different cultural traditions are forced into an awkward taxonomy, based on habitual associations widespread among the American reading public.

Metadata are in most cases heterogeneous, incomplete, and oftentimes rooted in self-contradictory classifications (vocabularies). Glaring inconsistencies occur both in

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professional library standards (such as BISAC, <https://bisg.org/page/BISACEdition>, and BIC, <https://bic.org.uk/files/pdfs/101201%20bic2.1%20complete%20rev.pdf>, WGSneu, https://vlb.de/assets/images/wgsneuversion2_0.pdf) and in the crowd sourcing and multi-language environment, where different linguistic and cultural traditions interfere, not to mention the categories' contingency on a given editor's opinion and education. Most library classifications derive from the Dewey Decimal Classification and replicate its quadruple division of literary texts into "poetry", "fiction", "drama", and "collections" encompassing different genres. Categories are not exclusive. For example, BIG has separate classes for "Literature and Literary Studies" and "Fiction and related items". In WGSneu, the genres lyric and drama appear twice on different levels, once in their pure form and once as a mixture of both in the ballad (both on the same level of classification). Predictably, one does not see much improvement in the collections based on crowd sourcing. Thus, in the English Wikisource, there is a separate category "Works by genre", which includes "fiction" and "drama"; however, on a deeper level, "fiction" includes "plays". The German classification (<https://de.wikisource.org/wiki/Wikisource:Systematik#Textgattung>) is much more exhaustive and bears a more systematic character in comparison with the English one. But even in this case one comes across striking omissions and inconsistencies, for example the genre "drama" contains the subgenres "comedy" and "dialogs", while "tragedy" is missing. Moreover, "dialogs" historically represent (philosophical, scholarly) prose and so they by no means belong in the dramatic category. An exemplary classification can be found in the Polish Wikisource, where all literary texts are divided into the three major genres of drama, lyric, and epic, distinguished on the basis of the distribution of voices in relation to the represented world and branching out into diverse subgenres. In this they correspond with the Universal Decimal Classification and the Dewey Decimal Classification.

In recent years, metadata initiatives have aimed at providing shared and robust categories for describing the content of collections: Dublin Core, Text Encoding Initiative, and the ontologies CIDOC CRM and FRBRoo (mentioned in section 3.5, in reference to

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our haiku use case). In the outlook of this report and specifically in D6.1, we propose our own model for metadata, derived from the Metamodel for Corpus Metadata and compliant with CIDOC CRM as a base ontology but intended for literary collections and containing a controlled vocabulary that enriches the Dewey Decimal Classification with the categories of present-day literary studies. An extension of CIDOC CRM, our model should also be Dublin Core and FRBRoo compliant.

4.5. Access to Corpus Data: Retrieval Tools (GUI, APIs, OAI-PMH)

Retrieval and visualization bring life to corpora and take place through interfaces. However, the design of retrieval tools may pose a major obstacle for the propagation of CLS as even some CLARIN specialists admit to being intimidated by some interfaces. The reason for the unease lies in the plethora of methods that can be selected through the graphic interface and applied to a text or a text collection. Many CLS tools, developed independently of one another, make a claim to universality, hence the overabundance of options.

Opinions differ on the relation between retrieval tools and corpus design. Some are inclined to perceive user interfaces as an external service provided by IT departments, while others recognize in the presetting of possible queries a crucial constituent of the corpus design process. The notion of programmable corpora, central to the CLS INFRA project, harmonizes with the latter approach. Bespoke or site-specific interfaces enjoy widespread use. The Deutsche Referenzkorpus (DeReKo) exemplifies a corpus with tailor-made interfaces (COSMAS II and KorAP). Digital critical editions can be regarded as corpora endowed with very specific interfaces allowing the comparison of different versions or the visualization of the creative process.

In CLS, the research situation usually involves a separate text corpus and a retrieval tool or a general environment/toolbox for data visualization and analysis, such as CQP (Evert and Hardie 2011), KorAP (Diewald et al. 2016), ANNIS (Krause, Leser and Lüdeling 2016), or <https://voyant-tools.org/>, or all resources listed on <https://www.clarin.eu/content/tools> and <https://tapor.ca/home> (the latter being the source

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of D6.1's list of tools). To those general-purpose tools developed in the framework of CLS the researcher feeds (uploads) appropriate text collections to compute and visualize some aspects of textual data. Some resources combine the features of digital collections and visualization tools, for example DraCor, Textgrid, DTA, or GAMS, or some projects hosted by Stanford Literary Lab.

Another level of the revival of information from literary corpora entails programming, mostly in R and Python. The collections can be either downloaded locally or contacted remotely by way of using APIs (Application Programming Interfaces), i.e. software intermediaries that broker between two applications, for example our power shell and a text database. A few collections provide APIs: Folger Shakespeare Library, DraCor, Deutsches Textarchiv, or TextGrid. In DraCor, for example, the researcher can remotely obtain the list of plays in the corpus, the text of a play in the TEI format, the network of characters, stage directions, etc.

Metadata of different repositories, which are vital for interoperability, can be accessed by the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH).

5. Legal and Ethical Considerations

Our quest for the Slovak novel aims at enhancing the visibility of an unjustly marginalized and yet central (Central) European culture. It has been said that a person cannot read more than ten thousand books in his or her life; this limited lifespan has become a factor in the power struggles shaping the notion of the canonical, which is central to our first use case tracing the presence of the haiku in various collections and, by extension, various cultures. The advent of “distant reading” came along with the promise of moving beyond the narrow canon towards a truly cosmopolitan understanding of world literature. Franco Moretti's conception of “distant reading” gained traction exactly in the context of the so-called “canon wars” because it promised to enhance the inclusivity of literary studies. Thanks to computers, the “great unread” can be at last taken into consideration in the process of creating the general image of the cultural output of humanity (on the notion of

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the “great unread”, see Tautz and Simpson 2020²³). In a sense, the Digital Humanities can contribute to “social justice” or “restorative justice”, either directed at the present woes²⁴ or at history. Admittedly, historical archives are biased and violent because they reproduce the interests and biases of the rulers and the colonizers.²⁵ The second stage of silencing takes place in the moment of digitization as another selection procedure applies. However, with literary collections, vast as they are, we may well have reached the point that the suppression takes place not only at the borders separating the archive from the non-archive, but also inside the archive itself. The metaphor of the gatekeeper may soon be replaced by that of an evil troll who obliterates the traces within the archives. The authors of the present review remain alert to both perils. Many texts and collections are systematically overlooked – for the reasons we discuss at length in chapters three and four.

In this chapter, we point out both ethical and legal issues of data management; further on, we present lawful solutions to burning research desiderata. We refrain from philosophizing on the relation between law and ethical values; however, one cannot help noticing that the underlying notion of the two fields is responsibility. One manages data responsibly²⁶ to prevent being held responsible and because it is right. In most countries and at the EU level, researchers are legally obliged to ethically assess their research; research funding institutions also formulate guidelines concerning best practices in data

²³ Since Goethe coined the notion of world literature, the whole issue of the Goethe-Jahrbuch in which Tautz and Simpson’s intervention appears is very instructive.

²⁴ Examples of using the methods of the Digital Humanities: tracing families separated at the USA-Mexican border (<https://xpmethod.columbia.edu/epistemic-action/2018-06-25-torn-apart.html>), following the flow of refugees into Europe (<https://www.lucify.com/the-flow-towards-europe/>), or saving the Ukrainian cultural heritage from the Russian invaders (<https://www.sucho.org/>) (footnote based on the keynote at Dhd 2022 in Potsdam).

²⁵ In this context, one should mention the initiative CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance: <https://www.gida-global.org/care>. The title acronym stands for “Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics”.

²⁶ On the ethical aspects of research data management, see: <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/>; <https://www.zotero.org/groups/439756/forschungsdaten>; <https://www.forschungsdaten.info/themen/ethik-und-gute-wissenschaftliche-praxis/>; <https://www.forschungsdaten.org/index.php/Hauptseite>.

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management.²⁷ It seems, though, that ethical norms bear a more universal character than legal regulations, even in a unifying Europe.

The FAIR principles serve as guidelines and also evaluation criteria (Odebrecht and Belz 2023 forthcoming) for practices involving data. Especially the quality of the reusability of data coincides with ethical and legal requirements, for example that data affecting people be anonymized or/and pseudonymized. As with all general standards, the challenge consists in applying general criteria to specific cases (the hermeneutical *Anwendung*).

Admittedly, CLS does not concern itself (mainly) with living people; one might be tempted to believe that ethical and ensuing legal concerns have a lesser impact on the discipline. (With respect to personal data of researchers or participants in CLS projects, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) applies.) Nevertheless, CLS explores cultural legacy, which means it bears upon individual and collective identity. This being the case, CLS bears responsibility for many political and societal issues, for example those described with reference to the representativeness and the balance of a corpus in chapter four.

Data are always provided by a living person, to which all ethical and legal considerations apply. Fostering the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data means expanding the purview of Open Access and thus making scholarly literature and data sets free of financial and other barriers. “Free access to scientific and scholarly information for everyone, everywhere – that is Open Access”, as the authors of the platform <https://open-access.network/> put it in accordance with the so-called Budapest Declaration (2002), which tries to balance the pathos of openness with an individual’s right to having his or her creation and property at his or her command. The said platform offers not only information about Open Access, but also training and networking opportunities. Among the sources that provide vital information on the topic are Sherpa Juliet, a searchable database of “up-to-date information concerning research

²⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm.

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funders' policies and their requirements on open access, publication and data archiving" (<https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/juliet/about.html>). Its twin resource Sherpa Romeo aggregates and analyzes journal publishers' policies concerning copyright and achieving open access (<https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/>).

Whether we are using ready-found resources or make the results of our work available for someone else's research, licenses set limits of reusability. Different kinds of licenses pertain to different kinds of information: Reactive Commons is suitable for texts, illustrations, and data, GNU General Public License (GPL) was designed for software, Open Data Commons (ODC) is for data banks, and Community Data License Agreement (CDLA) regulates open data sharing. Of course, each of the licenses offers a wealth of options: in the case of the most general and popular service provider for standardized license texts, Creative Commons, the CC BY type "lets others distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon your work, even commercially, as long as they credit you for the original creation".²⁸

However, the decision as to the legal situation of the literary material or the contents of the corpus does not entirely lie with a researcher – the copyright weighs in on the design of research.

As Schöch et al. (2020) put it, it is "an open secret of the Digital Humanities" that a window of opportunity is open for CLS with regard to the available textual resources. The window opens around 1800 due to the technical challenges earlier texts cause to the Optical Character Recognition (OCR) and closes again around 1920. The latter date holds true because, as a general rule, copyright protection lasts for seventy years after an author's death. Thus, the compilation and sharing of text collections with third parties becomes more complicated when newer texts come into question. This brings about, Schöch et al. (2020) continue, the unfortunate consequence that the setting of research priorities is often primarily determined not by the cognitive interests and goals of the research itself, but essentially by technical and legal factors. Consequently, state-of-the-art research with more recent texts is only possible to a limited extent.

²⁸ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>

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There are generally five practical approaches to overcoming the legal limitations, the last three being formulated or developed or at least strongly supported by researchers contributing to CLS Infra.

In the closed room model, researchers work in a technically isolated environment – usually on a workstation computer available on site and using individually developed analysis programs – to gain access to text holdings of a specific institution. This kind of access, which is provided by numerous libraries in their reading rooms, unfortunately entails substantial practical and organizational efforts, while the results may not necessarily be worth such exertion. The procedure responds rather to the need to read a rare book as it does not allow for combining resources.

The second solution consists in the work with a closed interface; data providers make certain text collections and analysis tools available from the browser. The disadvantage of this model is that the researchers cannot view, download, modify, or add to the data themselves or combine data sets from different sources.

The three solutions supported by and developed in CLS INFRA include:

Querying licensed resources with the help of Application Programming Interfaces (API, see section 4.5). The authors of DraCor.org and of the conception of programmable corpora (Fischer et al. 2019) which provides CLS INFRA with a conceptual backbone have concentrated on the development of the API approach to textual collections in general and DraCor in particular.

Serving as an example of the second solution, which we would like to call “encapsulation”, the whole Dracor research ecosystem can be downloaded with Docker (<https://www.docker.com/get-started/>) to handle copyrighted material offline. This solution will likely become increasingly popular with researchers and providers of smart literary data as it dovetails with HathiTrust’s Data Capsules (<https://wiki.htrc.illinois.edu/display/COM/HTRC+Data+Capsule+Environment>).

Finally and thirdly, Schöch et al. (2020) put forward as a solution “derived text formats”. In this case, copyrighted textual materials are transformed before publication in such a way that copyright-relevant features are removed, but the use of various relevant

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methods of text and data mining (TDM) remains possible. The copyrighted text collections undergo transformation into derived text formats through the use of workflows, which essentially can entail both an information enrichment (e.g. through linguistic annotation) and an information reduction (e.g. by deleting the word forms or eliminating the sequence information). The simplest example of such a derived text format would be a table that records the frequencies of each word in each text for a set of texts.

Of course, the practical solutions are only temporary. Our discipline demands legal and sustainable solutions that will bolster its ethical foundations and credentials.

6. Outlook

In this data landscape review, we have focused on machine-readable collections of literary texts as a surprisingly undertheorized central artifact, foundation, and output of research conducted in the framework of CLS. With an eye to enhancing intellectual access to reusable data and the interoperational reusability of already accessible data, we have done our best to align our discourse with the general FAIR principles without losing sight of our particular research cases. This oscillation between the abstract and the concrete has helped us to account for the tectonic shift brought about by CLS in the understanding of the basic notions of literariness, text, and collection. Still, the core of our conceptual work lies in chapter four, where we describe the makeup and different dimensions of corpora. We hope that the typology we propose will help researchers in gathering material appropriate for their interests and that the main considerations concerning corpus design will facilitate their interaction with available corpora as well as the construction of their own textual collections. Interaction with corpora likewise concerns the many ways of retrieving information considered in chapter four in its debatable relation to corpus design. Continuing with the topic of the interaction with collections, which fills them with life while also having an impact on real life issues, we pointed in chapter five to some basic ethical and legal issues, united by the general notion of responsibility in data management. The topic of data management is covered in great detail in CLS IFRA's Data Management Plan. Nevertheless, the indispensable complement of this review is

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above all Deliverable 6.1 “Inventory of existing data sources and formats”, which we cordially invite you to read.

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